

Explore the Lifetime Frontier with MATHUSLA

Cristiano Alpigiani

on behalf of the MATHUSLA Collaboration

W

UNIVERSITY of
WASHINGTON

19th April 2018

Alps 2018

MATHUSLA

The Hidden Sector

- The Standard Model (SM) is in amazing agreement with the experimental data, but **still some problems remain unsolved**: dark matter, neutrinos masses, hierarchy, matter-antimatter asymmetry...
- Many extensions of the SM (Hidden Valley, Stealth SUSY, 2HDM, baryogenesis models, etc) include particles that are **neutral, weakly coupled**, and **long-lived** that can decay to final states containing several hadronic jets
- Long-lived particles (LLPs) occur naturally in **coupling to a hidden sector (HS)** via small scalar (Higgs) or vector (γ , Z) portal couplings

❖ Wide range of possible lifetimes from $\mathcal{O}(mm)$ up to $\mathcal{O}(m/km)$

The mixing of Higgs with HS results in a Higgs like particle decaying into LLPs:

small coupling \rightarrow long lifetimes [Phys. Lett. B6512 374-379, 2007]

$\sim 10^8$ Higgs boson @ HL-LHC

Many Searches at LHC...

- Strong dependence on the sub-detectors of ATLAS, CMS and LHCb
- Detector signature depends of production and decay operators of a given model

• LHC detector searches limited by large backgrounds

- ✓ Large QCD jet production
- ✓ Pile-up problems
- ✓ Beam halo issues
- ...

➔ Need a background-free detector!

...and who ya gonna call?

MATHUSLA!

MATHUSLA detector → **MA**ssive **T**iming **H**odoscope for **U**ltra **S**table neutral **L**p**A**rticles

- Dedicated detector **sensitive to neutral long-lived particles that have lifetime up to the Big Bang Nucleosynthesis** (BBN) limit ($10^7 - 10^8$ m) for the HL-LHC
- **Large-volume, air filled detector located on the surface** above and somewhat displaced from ATLAS or CMS interaction points
- HL-LHC → **order of $N_h = 1.5 \times 10^8$** Higgs boson produced

- Observed decays:

$$N_{\text{obs}} \sim N_h \cdot \text{Br}(h \rightarrow \text{ULLP} \rightarrow \text{SM}) \cdot \epsilon_{\text{geometric}} \cdot \frac{L}{bc\tau}$$

ϵ = geometrical acceptance along ULLP

L = size of the detector along ULLP direction

$b \sim m_h / (n \cdot m_X) \leq 3$ for Higgs boson decaying to $n = 2$, $m_X \geq 20$ GeV

- ❖ To collect a few ULLP decays with $c\tau \sim 10^7$ m require a 20 m detector along direction of travel of ULLP and about 10 % geometrical acceptance

$$L \sim (20 \text{ m}) \left(\frac{b}{3}\right) \left(\frac{0.1}{\epsilon_{\text{geometric}}}\right) \frac{0.3}{\text{Br}(h \rightarrow \text{ULLP})}$$

MATHUSLA detector → **MA**ssive **T**iming **H**odoscope for **U**ltra **S**table neutral **p**Articles

➤ Large area **surface detector** ($200 \times 200 \text{ m}^2$) above an LHC p-p IP dedicated to detection of ultra long-lived particles

➤ Air decay volume with **tracking chambers** **surrounded by scintillators**

❖ Need robust tracking

❖ Excellent background rejection

→ **RPCs** planes are an attractive choice (**good space and time resolution** for vertex reconstruction and cosmic ray rejection)

→ **Scintillator** planes for redundant background rejection – timing

But other technologies can be investigated for the main detector

HL-LHC Sensitivity Estimate

- Decay of Higgs boson to pair of scalars for different masses m_X
- No QCD background \rightarrow big sensitivity gain

200 x 200 x 20 m³

USS Gerald R. Ford in facts and figures

From C. Young

Propulsion

2 nuclear reactors, 4 shafts
Each reactor is capable of producing 300MW of electricity

Displacement

100,000 tons
As much as 400 Statues of Liberty

Speed

30+ knots
(55kmh)

Flight Deck

2.02ha
78m wide
2 runways

From C. Young

Where MATHUSLA could be located?

- We need a large surface close to a p-p interaction point (IP)

MATHUSLA could be located above either ATLAS (P1) or CMS (P2)

Where MATHUSLA could be located?

- ...not sure there is enough space around ATLAS...
- But CMS site has a large area that is owned by CERN and there are no plans to occupy it in the future!

What is the expected background
for MATHUSLA?

MATHUSLA - Backgrounds

J-P Chou, D. Curtin, H. Lubatti
arXiv 1606.06298

Non-collision backgrounds
can be measured when no
LHC collisions

No LHC QCD background, BUT...

- **Cosmic muon** rate of about 10 MHz (200 m²)
→ rejected with scintillator timing (**1.5 ns timing resolution**)

- LHC collision backgrounds

- ✓ **LHC muons** about 10 Hz

→ Reject with scintillator timing and entrance hit position

- ✓ LHC neutrinos (subdominant background) → MATHUSLA should observe a few events during HL-LHC data taking period

- **Upward atmospheric neutrinos** that interact in air decay volume

- ✓ Estimate Low rate ~ 70 events per year above 300 MeV

- ✓ Mostly “decay” to low momentum proton → reject with time of flight

Goal is a background-free MATHUSLA!

MATHUSLA - Background Simulations

Effort underway to develop simulations of all the sources of backgrounds

- Current plan to deal with **muons** and **neutrinos traveling upwards** is to create a “gun” that shoots particles into MATHUSLA
- Cosmic ray showers simulated using **CORSIKA** (work is well advance!)
- Atmospheric neutrinos simulated using **GENIE**

... but simulation need to be anchored to real data!

...so we need a...

MATHUSLA test stand...

MATHUSLA Test Stand

Top and bottom scintillator layers from Tevatron DØ provided by Dmitri Denisov

- MC simulations need data with LHC colliding protons and also when the beam is off
- Test stand assembled last October thanks to the big help of CMS and ATLAS!
- The goal is to measure charged tracks from LHC, not to search for LLP

3 layers of RPCs provided by University of Tor Vergata (Rome) by Rinaldo Santonico (from Argo Experiment)

Excellent for students participation at all stages of an experiment: design, test components, install, take data and analysis

Installation in ATLAS P1 (1)

- Cosmic background well understood
- Need to quantify the **background from ATLAS**
- Test stand installed in the (Buffer Zone) on the surface area above ATLAS (exactly above IP) in November (during ATLAS operations this space is empty)
 - ✓ Perform measurements with beam on and off

Installation in ATLAS P1 (2)

Henry L. putting the last bolt

P1 data-taking lasted < 2 weeks

MATHUSLA @ H8

- With the opening of the ATLAS cavern, the buffer zone was filled with ATLAS radioactive material (beam pipe shielding, etc...)
- At the **end of November MATHUSLA test stand moved to a temporary space in CERN Preveessin** (H8 SPS extraction line)
 - Performed test with cosmic rays
 - Improved data-taking
 - Improved performance of the RPCs

MATHUSLA Performance (Scintillators & RPC)

Is MATHUSLA only LLP?

MATHUSLA - Cosmic Rays

- MATHUSLA could perform **cosmic rays studies at PeV energies**
- MATHUSLA will provide **quality data on EAS with better resolution than past and present experiments**
- **In stand alone mode**
 - MATHUSLA will provide measurements of **EAS direction, core position, density and time distributions** (assuming no e/μ separation)
 - MATHUSLA could be used to measure the all-particle energy spectrum, study the cosmic ray anisotropies, study muon content of very inclined events, test hadronic models, and possibly perform composition studies
- **In combined mode with CMS/ATLAS**
 - MATHUSLA will provide data on the **muon content of EAS** with $E_\mu > 50\text{-}70$ GeV for vertical incidence
 - MATHUSLA will extend the test of hadronic models and permit to study other EAS phenomena such as muon bundles and may be, the composition of cosmic rays
- Muons from nucleus-nucleus interaction events at the collider points might be also studied with MATHUSLA, allowing to discriminate between hadronic models.

J.C. Arteaga-Velázquez, A. Fernández-Téllez,
K. S. Caballero-Mora, M. Rodríguez-Cahuantzi,
M. A. Subieta-Vásquez

What about the future?

MATHUSLA - Next Steps

- MATHUSLA theory **white paper** is expected to be public soon
- Plan to make a report at the **Physics Beyond Colliders** CERN working group (<http://pbc.web.cern.ch/>)
- Working on a **MATHUSLA paper** focusing on test stand results and **MATHUSLA Letter Of Intent** - by the end of 2018
- We can think to construct a building of $200 \times 200 \text{ m}^2$, but...
- Some early thoughts on **modularity** to simplify construction and for incremental deployment e.g. $100 \times (20 \text{ m} \times 20 \text{ m} \times 20 \text{ m})$ boxes
- Lots of work still need to be done:
 - Details design
 - Simulation
 - Extending CR physics case ...
- Require funding $O(\text{tens M}\$)$ + manpower

Conclusions

- We are studying the feasibility of a large scale detector to measure LLPs with very long lifetimes
- Several studies have already been performed
- A test module has been installed on the ATLAS surface area in November 2017
- Background tests above ATLAS will re-start in May and continue until the end of LHC Run 2 operations
- Aiming to prepare a **letter of intent** by the end of the year

Conclusions

- We are studying the feasibility of a large scale detector to measure LLPs with very long lifetimes
 - Several studies have already been performed
 - A test module has been installed on the ATLAS
 - Background tests above ATLAS will re-start in Mid-2018 during LHC Run 2 operations
 - Aiming to prepare a **letter of intent** by the end of 2018
 - **If we want to help...we have also rum!**
- ❖ **Contacts:**
- Cristiano.Alpigiani@cern.ch
 - mathusla.experiment@cern.ch

BACKUP

Higgs Boson Decay Modes

- Combined ATLAS-CMS Run 1 results w.r.t. standard model expectations
- **Good agreement with SM...BUT...**

BUT > 30% BSM allowed

LLP Searches in the LHC Detectors

Image courtesy of
Heather Russell

Displaced hadronic jets
in the inner detector

Displaced
leptons in the
inner detector

Emerging
jets

.....

Displaced hadronic jets in
the muon spectrometer

Displaced jets in
the hadronic
calorimeter

LHC Detector Signatures

- Strong dependence on the sub-detectors of ATLAS, CMS and LHCb.
 - Inner detectors, calorimeters and muon systems not the same in the three detectors
 - All LHC detectors need to overcome obstacles
- Boost of LLP determines opening angle(s) and that affects trigger efficiencies.
 - Efficiencies can also depend on trigger algorithm and subsystem readout at trigger level
 - Presents a challenge for generic, model independent searches

Signature Space of Displaced Vertex Searches

- Detector signature depends of production and decay operators of a given model
 - Production determines cross section and number and characteristics of associated objects
 - Decay operator coupling determines life time, which is effectively a free parameter
- Common Production modes
 - Production of single object - with No associated objects (AOs)
 - Higgs-like scalar Φ that decays to a pair of long-lived scalars, ss , that each in turn decay to quark pairs – Hidden Valley, Neutral Naturalness, ...
 - Vector (γ_{dark}, Z') mixing with SM gauge bosons – kinetic mixing
 - Production of a single object P with an AO – Many SUSY models
 - AO jets if results from decay of a colored object
 - AO leptons if LLP produced via EW interactions with SM
- Common detector signatures \Rightarrow generic searches

Neutral Long-lived Particles

- Neutral LLPs lead to displaced decays with no track connecting to the IP, a distinguishing signature
 - SM particles predominantly yield prompt decays (good news)
 - SM cross sections very large (eg. QCD jets) (bad news)
- To reduce SM backgrounds many Run 1 ATLAS searches required two identified displaced vertices or one displaced vertex with an associated object
 - Resulted in good rejection of rare SM backgrounds
 - BUT limited the kinematic region and/or lifetime reach
- None the less, these Run 1 searches were able to probe a broad range of the LLP parameter space (LLP-mass, LLP- $c\tau$)
- ATLAS search strategy for displaced decays - based on signature driven triggers that are detector dependent

Some of the LLP Models

Baryogenesis
wino-like model

Baryogenesis
Higgs portal

Low/high
mass bosons
to scalars

Z' models

Stealth SUSY

MATHUSLA – DAQ and Trigger

Test module DAQ

➤ **Scintillators:** PMTs interfaced with a VME crate connected to a PC

➤ **RPCs: Argo Experiment Local Station** (from Lecce). Data from each RPC acquired from a Receiver Card which reads out and digitises the space and time information from 10 pick-up pads and gives out the pad multiplicity for trigger purposes. On trigger occurrence the Local Station sends the collected data to the PC

Test module trigger

Two possible triggers: top and bottom scintillators in coincidence, with:

1. Timing appropriate for downward going particle (cosmic ray events can be used for space and time alignment)
2. Timing appropriate for upward going particle

MATHUSLA - Scintillators Support Details (1)

MATHUSLA – Scintillators Support Details (2)

- Tapped holes not through holes.
- Soft rubber spacers between the shim and detector to evenly distribute the clamping force.
- Working on eliminating the side clamps entirely - requires a different alignment.
- Assembly test with two small scintillators this week.
- Will tweak some of the shim dimensions based on our assembly test.

Shim simple design

MATHUSLA – Scintillators Support Details (3)

- Preliminary- NOT FINAL
- Options to explore
 - Get -channel at CERN and add slots
 - Do in US but then have shipping costs
 - To be continued

MATHUSLA - Trigger Development (1)

Courtesy of
Audrey Kvam

Definition of TOP (similarly for BOTTOM)

MATHUSLA - Trigger Development (1)

Courtesy of
Audrey Kvam

Putting together (some of) trigger in 175

SLAC

1. Disc + first level OR logic
 - a. TOP
 - b. BOTTOM
2. Second level OR + AND between TOP & BOTTOM
3. Prescaler
4. Delay boxes
5. OR for 4 triggers
6. Controller
7. TDC
8. ADC
9. Input Register

MATHUSLA – Signal Simulation

MATHUSLA detector → MAssive Timing Hodoscope for Ultra Stable neutral pArticles

MATHUSLA – Main Detector

MATHUSLA detector → **M**Assive **T**iming **H**odoscope for **U**ltra **S**table neutral **L**p **A**rticles

- Scintillators array : 5016 scintillators 2x1x0.1 [m]
 - Roof array : 2508 scintillators
 - Floor array : 2508 scintillators
 - Material: polyvinyltoluene
- Main building structure : consist in several blocks and two base platforms
 - Materials: steel and concrete + air environment

Courtesy of Martin Subieta

Main detector layout simulation

MATHUSLA - Cosmic Muon Background Event

MATHUSLA – Scalar LLP Lifetime Constraints

- A recent paper [A. Fradette and M. Pospelov, arXiv:1706.01920v1] examines the BBN lifetime bound on lifetimes of long-lived particles in the context of constraints on a scalar model coupled through the Higgs portal, where the production occurs via $h \rightarrow ss$, where the decay is induced by the small mixing angle of the Higgs field h and scalar s .
- For $m_s > m_\pi$ the lifetime $\tau < 0.1$ s.
- Conclusion does not depend strongly on $BR(h \rightarrow ss)$

MATHUSLA White Paper - Organisation

1. Foreword
2. Introduction
3. Summary of MATHUSLA experiment
4. Letters of Support
5. LLPs at the LHC and MATHUSLA
6. Theory Motivation for ULLPs: Naturalness
7. Theory Motivation for ULLPs: Dark Matter
8. Theory Motivation for ULLPs: Baryogenesis
9. Theory Motivation for ULLPs: Neutrinos
10. Theory Motivation for ULLPs: Bottom-Up Considerations
11. Signatures
12. Cosmic Ray Physics prospects with MATHUSLA
13. Conclusions

MATHUSLA – Cosmic Neutrinos Background

No LHC QCD background, BUT...

- Cosmic neutrinos traveling upwards that have inelastic interactions in the decay volume

❖ This background can be measured when there is no beam in the LHC!

MATHUSLA Test Module: Scintillator Planes

- Layout for the 2 scintillator planes

D0 forward MUON
Trigger scintillator:
12.8-mm-thick BICRON
404A of trapezoidal shape +
WLS bars for light collection

Clamps

U-Channel

MATHUSLA - Scintillators Details

MATHUSLA - RPC Details

- 12 RPCs and DAQ from the prototype of ARGO cosmic ray shower experiment in Tibet
- Operating in streamer mode
- Chamber size: 1.25 x 2.80 m²
- 10 Pads (55.6 x 61.8 cm²) for each RPC
- 8 Strips (6.75 x 61.8 cm²) for each Pad
- Gas Ar mixed with the ATLAS RPC gas (C₂H₂F₄/Iso-C₄H₁₀/SF₆ (94.7/5/0.3))

Installation in ATLAS P1 (2)

Detail A
Scale: 1:75

MATHUSLA and Cosmic Rays

- The combination of a **large area detector** of atmospheric showers (e and μ meas.) with a **LHC detector** (only μ meas.) provides a more complete picture of air showers

Muon bundles at LHC

*Courtesy of Rinaldo Santonico and
Arturo Fernandez Tellex*

MATHUSLA Performance (Scintillators & RPC)

A very rough tracking!

MATHUSLA Performance - RPC

➤ Number of event per pad

MATHUSLA Performance - RPC

➤ Number of event per strip

Scintillator Preliminary Cost Evaluation

From C. Young

- Scintillator

- Top and bottom area = $2 \times 200 \text{ m}^2 = 80\,000 \text{ m}^2$
- Sides = $4 \times 200 \times 20 \text{ m}^2 = 16\,000 \text{ m}^2$
- Total area = $96\,000 \text{ m}^2$
- Assume thickness = 1 cm, density = 1 gm/cm^3
- Assume 3 USD / kg (low end of NO_vA estimates)
excluding electronics
- Total cost ~ 3M USD

RPC Preliminary Cost Evaluation

From R. Santonico

Cost evaluation for 10^5 m² RPC total area

- A first evaluation is of about 75-80 ME
- The mechanical support has a strong incidence on this cost and, in my opinion, a more precise project on how we support the MATHUSLA detector would allow to optimize the RPC support thus saving some 10 ME or more
- This evaluation does not include the detector services: Gas system, Power system, DAQ. Can be included next week.
- Concerning the time and amplitude acquisition we can count on the next FE circuit generation (by R. Cardarelli), giving the rise and fall times in digital form

MATHUSLA White Paper

- Collaboration of 70+ theorists
- Aiming for publication in 2017

Detecting Ultra-Long-Lived Particles: The MATHUSLA Physics Case

Editors:

David Curtin¹, Marco Drewes², Matthew McCullough³, Patrick Meade⁴, Rabindra Mohapatra¹, Michele Papucci⁵, Jessie Shelton⁶, Brian Shuve⁷

Contributors: B. Batell, Timothy Cohen, Nathaniel Craig, Csaba Csaki, Yanou Cui, Francesco D'Eramo, B. Dev, Keith Dienes, Marco Drewes, Rouven Essig, Jared Evans, Marco Farina, Thomas Flacke, Claudia Frugiuele, Elina Fuchs, Dmitry Gorbunov, M. Graesser, Peter Graham, C. Hagedorn, Lawrence Hall, Philip Harris, J. Helo, M. Hirsch, Yonit Hochberg, Anson Hook, A. Ibarra, Seyda Ipek, Sunghoon Jung, S. King, Simon Knapen, Joachim Kopp, Gordan Krnjaic, Eric Kuflik, Salvator Lombardo, Rabindra Mohapatra, S. Moretti, Duccio Pappadopulo, Gilad Perez, David Pinner, Maxim Pospelov, Matthew Reece, Rick S., Brian Shuve, Daniel Stolarski, Brooks Thomas, Yuhsin Tsai, Brock Tweedie, Stephen West, Y. Zhang, Kathryn Zurek, ...

MATHUSLA Collaboration

University of Washington Seattle, Tel Aviv University, University of Toronto, Autonomous University of Puebla, Rutgers State University of New Jersey, SLAC, Università di Tor Vergata, Università della Calabria, Sapienza Università di Roma and CERN

Cristiano Alpigiani	Cristiano.Alpigiani@cern.ch	University of Washington - Seattle
Audrey Katherine Kvam	audrey.katherine.kvam@cern.ch	University of Washington - Seattle
Henry Lubatti	lubatti@u.washington.edu	University of Washington - Seattle
Mason Louis Proffitt	mason.louis.proffitt@cern.ch	University of Washington - Seattle
Joseph Rothberg	Joseph.Rothberg@cern.ch	University of Washington - Seattle
Gordon Watts	gwatts@uw.edu	University of Washington - Seattle
Emma Torró Pastor	emma.torro.pastor@cern.ch	University of Washington - Seattle
Yan Benhammou	Yan.Benhammou@cern.ch	Tel Aviv University
Meny Ben Moshe	Menyb@post.tau.ac.il	Tel Aviv University
Tingting Cao	Tingting.cao@cern.ch	Tel Aviv University
Erez Etzion	Erez.Etzion@cern.ch	Tel Aviv University
Tamar Garbuz	tgarbuz137@gmail.com	Tel Aviv University
Gilad Mizrahi	giladmiz01@gmail.com	Tel Aviv University
Yiftah Silver	yiftahsi@gmail.com	Tel Aviv University
Abi Soffer	Abner.Soffer@cern.ch	Tel Aviv University
David Curtin	david.r.curtin@gmail.com	University of Toronto
Roberto Guida	Roberto.Guida@cern.ch	CERN

Mario Rodriguez Cahuantzi	mario.rodriguez.cahuantzi@cern.ch	Autonomous University of Puebla
Martin Hentschinski	martin.hentschinski@gmail.com	Autonomous University of Puebla
Mario Ivan Martinez Hernandez	Mario.Martinez.Hernandez@cern.ch	Autonomous University of Puebla
Guillermo Tejada Munoz	Guillermo.Tejada.Munoz@cern.ch	Autonomous University of Puebla
Arturo Fernandez Tellez	Arturo.Fernandez.Tellez@cern.ch	Autonomous University of Puebla
Martin Alfonso Subieta Vasquez	martin.alfonso.subieta.vasquez@cern.ch	Autonomous University of Puebla
John Paul Chou	john.paul.chou@cern.ch	Rutgers, State University of New Jersey
Steffie Ann Thayil	steffie.ann.thayil@cern.ch	Rutgers, State University of New Jersey
Charlie Young	young@slac.stanford.edu	SLAC
Paolo Camarri	paolo.camarri@cern.ch	Università di Tor Vergata
Roberto Cardarelli	roberto.cardarelli@roma2.infn.it	Università di Tor Vergata
Rinaldo Santonic	santonic@roma2.infn.it	Università di Tor Vergata
Antonio Policicchio	Antonio.Policicchio@cern.ch	Sapienza Università di Roma
Marco Schioppa	Marco.Schioppa@cern.ch	Università della Calabria
Giovanni Marsella	giovanni.marsella@cern.ch	INFN Lecce e Università del Salento